

The La Serena School for Data Science: Tools for Data-Driven Sciences

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There is no question that the new generation of astronomers will do cutting-edge research by taking advantage of the increasingly large datasets that are becoming available. In preparation, the La Serena School for Data Science (LSSDS) seeks to provide late undergraduate and early graduate students with the tools needed to succeed in this area.

Every year the LSSDS receives over 200 applications from students of several countries to participate in this intensive school in computational and statistical techniques for data science. The school is offered to undergraduate students in the last years of their programs and graduate students in the first two years of their programs in areas such as astronomy, physics, biology, medical informatics, computer science, and statistics. The school typically accepts 32–36 applicants of many nationalities comprising ~50 % from US universities, with the remainder coming from Chilean institutions as well as other Latin American countries. Hosted annually at the AURA Recinto in La Serena, the school has gained popularity since it was launched in 2013. However, the 2020 school was canceled due to the COVID-19 pandemic, and the 2021 and 2022 sessions were offered online only.

As in previous years, the 2022 curriculum was crafted by the Scientific Organizing Committee (SOC) based partly on the content of the previous — and successful — schools and the feedback from former participants. The 2022 school had the

usual hands-on focus of the LSSDS, with lectures from international experts in several topics. Some of the subjects covered include supervised and unsupervised machine learning, Gaussian processes, databases, statistics, and deep learning, to name a few. The school also offered ‘Group

Projects’, where interdisciplinary and diverse groups of students applied the tools presented by solving various problems under the guidance of a professor. The online format included daily synchronous and asynchronous sessions during the 10-day program. The SOC limited the synchronous work to three hours per day via Zoom, targeting a total daily load of six to eight hours.

Instructors provided pre-recorded 45-minute lectures. The students were given access to the videos in advance, so that they could review the lectures on a daily basis and learn the theoretical concepts offered. During the first week, the synchronous time was used for answering questions about the lectures and to review and practice the hands-on material prepared by the instructors in the form of Jupyter Notebooks. During the second week, the school transitioned into the Group Projects, where groups of five

students worked together to solve a problem using the techniques learned during the first week. In total, we conducted eight Group Projects. An important addition to the online format was the participation of Teaching Assistants (TAs). We reached out to our former students from the 2017–2021 schools and invited them to participate as TAs.

Figures 1&2 (top and bottom, respectively): LSSDS students and staff from past LSSDS workshops. Credit: NOIRLab

Funding for their stipends came from the NSF grant and funding from partners in Latin America. The TAs had a crucial role, as they supported the learning of each group during the first week and the development of the Group Project. Additionally, the Local Organizing Committee (LOC) provided a 'school welcome package' to each student as a way to foster a sense of belonging to the school. The package included items that were useful during the school and some souvenirs from the AURA observatory.

The LSSDS offers a unique formative opportunity to introduce highly talented students to data science and big data in a diverse, international, and interdisciplinary environment guided by experts. We are now planning the 2023 session, which will be in-person. The school grants full scholarships to cover the roundtrip airfare from the home institutions to La Serena and room and board (except dinners) for the duration of the school.

In addition, the school includes a guided VIP visit to the AURA telescopes on Cerro Pachón and Cerro Tololo, with dinner and stargazing on Cerro Tololo.

Thanks to funding from NSF, along with other international partners, applications from students in US, Chilean, and Ecuadorian (members of CEDIA) institutions are eligible for full scholarships that cover all school expenses. Participants from any data-intensive field are welcome to apply. The announcement of the opening of applications will be made during January through the observatory social networks and the school website. We look forward to receiving your applications and meeting you in La Serena in August 2023!

Please visit [La Serena School for Data Science: Applied Tools for Data-Driven Sciences](#) to find further information about the school.

Figure 3: Web announcement graphic promoting the 2023 LSSDS workshop. Credit: NOIRLab